

Derivatisation : About 1 mg each of the samples were dissolved in 10 μ l of dried and distilled pyridine and to each 10 μ l of *N,O*-bis(trimethylsilyl)acetamide⁸ (Pierce Chemical, U.S.A.) was added and kept at 80° for 15 min. The sample (1-2 μ l) was injected into the gas chromatograph. The retention time of the various compounds have been given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compounds	Retention times (minutes)
α -Amyrin	8.4
Lupeol	9.6
Betulin	18.6
Methyl betulinate	11.6
Methyl oleanolate	19.4
Methyl ursolate	19.8

Acetyl derivatives of the methyl esters of oleanolic, betulinic and ursolic acids were also gas chromatographed on the same column. The retention times were found longer than those of the trimethylsilyl ethers. Moreover, there were considerable trailing of the peaks and no separation was observed in the case of betulinic and oleanolic acids.

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Chemical Examination of *Pterocarpus marsupium*

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The powdered heartwood of *Pterocarpus marsupium* was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and chloroform. The petroleum ether extract on chromatography (Si-gel, eluent chloroform) yielded a colourless compound (0.01%), m.p. 294°, [α]_D +74° (c 0.95 in CHCl₃) which was characterised as oleanolic acid [lit.¹ m.p. 310°, [α]_D +78° (CHCl₃)] the identity of which was confirmed with mixed m.p. and superimposable ir spectrum with an authentic sample. This is the first instance of oleanolic acid from a *Pterocarpus* species, eventhough

closely related acetyloleanolic acid has been found⁹ to be present in these woods.

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2a : R=H
2b : R=Me
2c : R=Ac

3a : R=H
3b : R=Me
3c : R=Ac

The petroleum ether extract also yielded pterostilbene (1) which we have reported⁸ earlier. The ¹³C nmr spectrum of pterostilbene (1) has now been recorded ; that of stilbenes appears to be scanty as reported in literature. The ¹³C {¹H} nmr spectrum (90 MHz ; DMSO-d₆) of compound 1 showed 10 signals corresponding to the 16 carbon atoms of its molecular formula. The multiplicities in the off-resonance spectrum were in agreement with the assignments. The spectrum showed signals at δ 128.28 (s, C-1'), 127.65 (d, C-2', 6'), 115.30 (d, C-3', 5') and 160.38 (s, C-4') assignable to the carbon atoms of the ring B, approximately comparable to the signals due to the corresponding carbons of *p*-cresol⁶ ; δ 157.13 (s, C-3, 5), 103.81 (d, C-2, 6), 98.99 (d, C-4) (the lone carbon appearing upfield by virtue of its *ortho*-relation to two oxygen functions on the aromatic rings) and 54.83 (OMe). Only one signal at δ 124.89 (d) was available to be assigned to both C- α and C- β . A signal at δ 139.35 (s) was tentatively assigned to C-1.

The chloroform extract on chromatography (Si-gel, eluent : chloroform-ethylacetate) gave compounds 2a and 3a. Compound 2a (0.012%), yellow prisms, crystallised from ethylacetate-chloroform, m.p. 200° ; C₁₅H₁₂O₄, M⁺ 256 ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1640 cm⁻¹ (chelated CO) ; λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 245 (3.96), 325 sh, 370 nm (4.45) ; was identified as 4,2',4'-trihydroxychalcone as its m.p.⁸ and uv data⁹ agreed with those reported. In the ¹H nmr spectrum of the compound 2a, the signals due to the

protons of the carbon skeleton were comparable to that reported⁷ in the case of 4,2'-dihydroxy-4'-methoxychalcone. Methylation and acetylation yielded the anticipated trimethyl ether⁸ (2b) and triacetate⁸ (2c), respectively; and their physical data agreed with those reported. The ¹³C{¹H} nmr (90 MHz, DMSO-d₆) spectrum of compound 2a, together with the off-resonance spectrum, showed signals at δ 191.26 (s, CO), 165.57 (s, C-2'), 164.81 (s, C-4'), 160.05 (s, C-4), 144.01 (d, C-β), 132.47 (d, C-6'), 130.90 (d, C-2, 6), 125.54 (s, C-1'), 117.14 (d, C-α), 115.67 (d, C-3, 5), 112.81 (s, C-1'), 107.98 (d, C-5) and 102.45 (d, C-3'); comparable to the signals due to the skeletal carbon atoms of the model compound 2'-hydroxy-4,4'-dimethoxychalcone⁹; nevertheless the anticipated⁹ six-line multiplet of C-α and C-β in the off-resonance spectrum could be observed only as doublets.

Compound 3a (0.009%); m.p. 207°, [α]_D -26° (c 0.99 in MeOH); C₁₈H₁₈O₆, M⁺ 256; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1650 cm⁻¹ (CO); $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) (log ϵ) 240 sh, 280 (4.30), 314 nm (1.72), was characterised as 7,4'-dihydroxyflavanone (liquiritigenin) as the reported m.p.¹⁰ and uv data⁹ agreed with the observed, and it gave a deep violet colour in the Shinoda test¹¹. The ¹H nmr spectrum of the compound 3a was in agreement with the spectrum reported⁷ for liquiritigenin. Methylation and acetylation of compound 3a resulted in the anticipated dimethyl ether (3b)¹² and diacetate (3c)¹⁰, respectively. In the ¹³C{¹H} nmr (90 MHz, DMSO-d₆) spectrum of the compound 3a, the signals due to the skeletal carbon atoms were comparable to that reported⁹ for 7,4'-dimethoxyflavanone. The off-resonance spectrum showed multiplicities supporting the assignments. The spectrum showed signals at δ 189.85 (s, CO), 164.33 (s, C-7), 162.86 (s, C-8a), 157.28 (s, C-4'), 129.06 (s, C-1'), 128.14 (d, C-5), 127.98 (d, C-2', 6'), 114.86 (s, C-4a), 113.29 (d, C-3', 5'), 110.20 (d, C-6), 102.29 (d, C-8), 78.72 (d, C-2), and 42.91 (t, C-3).

It is notable that optically active liquiritigenin has been isolated in the present investigation. Earlier workers¹³ who employed the method of alkali extraction and subsequent acidification for the isolation of this compound from several *Pterocarpus* woods, appears to have obtained a racemic form of it.

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Sterols of *Salsola foetida*†

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In the Ayurvedic system of medicine *Salsola foetida* (Chenopodiaceae) is highly used as vermifuge and the ashes of the plant are applied to itches¹. Some alkaloids have earlier been detected in *Salsola* species², but no report was found on their phyto-sterol composition. The chemical examination of the light petroleum extract of *S. foetida* has now resulted in the isolation of five sterols.

Experimental

Air-dried and powdered plant material (820 g) was extracted thrice with light petroleum for 36 h under reflux. After the usual work up light petroleum extract gave 5.32 g neutral extract, which after purification was subjected to column chromatographic separation over silica gel (~25 fold excess). Elution with light petroleum ether: benzene (1:1) gave a sterol fraction which exhibited positive Liberman-Burchard test and gave yellow colour with tetranitromethane. Its ir spectrum (KBr) revealed the presence of OH (1040, 3400 cm⁻¹) and C=C (1610 cm⁻¹) groups. It was crystallised from methanol and gave shining flakes, m.p. 130-32° (tlc-homogeneous, silica gel-5% AgNO₃, using several solvent systems). Since it was not found to be identical (m.m.p., co-tlc) with the available authentic specimen of sterols it was supposed to be a mixture which could not be separated further even by repeated column chromatography. For final confirmation the sterol fraction was then acetylated (Ac₂O-pyridine) and identification of each component was

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